

LEGAL FORMS OF HUMAN RIGHTS PROTECTION IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

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Annotation: This article describes the mechanism of human rights' protection, the prerequisites for the protection of personal rights in the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the fact that rights of population and dignity are the highest blessings, and the reforms implemented in our country in the protection of human rights in detail.

Keywords: Human rights, law, democracy, Constitution, principle, freedom.

INTRODUCTION

A person participates in all spheres of society and state life by exercising his rights, freedoms and duties established by state laws. Society and the state recognize the rights and freedom of a person, his honor and value as the highest value. This is reflected in Article 13 of the Constitution: "Democracy in the Republic of Uzbekistan is based on universal principles, according to which a person, his life, freedom, honor, dignity and other inviolable rights are the highest values."¹. The Constitution prioritizes the provision of human rights and freedoms, and does not consider a person to be a blessing of the administrative-ordering system, a simple means to achieve a set goal.

"Constitutional rights and freedoms apply to every person and every citizen of Uzbekistan. The distinctive feature of basic rights, freedoms and duties is that they are equal and the same for every person or every citizen without any exception.

¹ Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan. T. Uzbekistan. 2016

When the state recognizes one or another fundamental right, it creates the legal basis for the possibility of their implementation by everyone.²

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The chapter of our Constitution on the rights and freedoms of an individual or citizen is dedicated to specific rights and freedoms, and its articles form a logical system. These represent the specific features of rights and freedoms, the living standards of individuals and citizens. Based on these signs, constitutional rights and freedoms are divided into three groups: a) personal; b) political; d) can be divided into social and economic rights.

Personal rights and freedoms cover the main aspects of human freedom, represent the foundations of a person's life, living and activity in society, protect his personal life and private freedoms from various interferences.

Human life is a value of high social importance protected by law. Every person has the right to live, and no one can arbitrarily deprive him of it. This is also legally confirmed in Article 24 of the Constitution. "The right to create is an inherent right of every person. "An attempt on human life is the most serious crime."³

A person's place in society is determined by his personal rights and freedoms as well as by his opportunities to exercise political rights. Political rights determine how each person can participate in the political life and relations of society. "Citizens of the Republic of Uzbekistan have the right to join trade unions, political parties and other public associations, and participate in mass movements," stated in our national legislation. The more effectively a person uses his right to be a member of political organizations or public associations, it is important for his political maturity. Active participation of a person in political organizations and public associations expands his opportunities to realize and protect his identity.⁴

² H.B. Boboyev. Human rights T. Uzbekistan. 2017.

³ Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan. T. Uzbekistan. 2016 11 p

⁴ Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan. T. Uzbekistan. 2016 13-p

Social equality of a person is reflected in political rights. The practical expression of such equality is the ability of all citizens to effectively exercise political rights.

Economic right, by its essence, is the right to a certain social wealth. Such social assets are of various types and they provide the satisfaction of political, material and spiritual needs of citizens. According to Article 41 of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, everyone shall have the right to education. The state shall guarantee free secondary education. Schooling shall be under state supervision.⁵

Education should be focused on the full development of the human personality and its respect, should enable everyone to be a free and beneficial participant of the society, should establish friendship and respect among all peoples, races, ethnic and religious groups. It is necessary for all to agree to that.

According to Article 4 of the Law on Education, everyone's origin, sex, gender, language, age, race, nationality, faith, religion, social status, type of training, how long they have been in the territory of the republic everyone is guaranteed equal rights to education, regardless of where they live."

From the initial years of independence, Uzbekistan actively sought its own development path, this period was a period of striving to turn the Motherland into a free, strong and prosperous country. Access to the world community, the most optimal ways of interstate multilateral relations were sought. All these have led to the renewal of the society, which is unique to Uzbekistan. This way is a process of development that is fully compatible with the interests of the people of the republic, which has a constitutional basis, and is based on taking world experience into account as well as the lifestyle, traditions, and customs of our people in the formation of a socially oriented market economy. The main goal of comprehensive reforms implemented in Uzbekistan is to create decent living conditions for people. Thanks

⁵ Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan. T. Uzbekistan. 2016 16-p

to independence, the centuries-old dreams of our people came true, the nation's pride, honor, and dignity were restored. Every citizen was lucky to live according to his dreams and hopes, to live freely and prosperously.

The main law of our country is the legal guarantee of democratic development of the country. Human rights are one of the universally recognized principles of a democratic society. Humanitarian ideas aimed at protecting human rights were also reflected in the development of our statehood in the past. If we pay attention to the meaning of the term "constitution", it means "establishment", "regulation", "structure", "creation". The historical development of mankind shows that wherever democracy takes root, rights are guaranteed and the issue of equality of citizens is specially noted. Human rights are related to the birth of a person. The concept of rights is a value that has been living in our land for centuries. Human rights were highly respected in the state of the Somanids, Khorezmshahs, Timur and Timurids from the time of ancient Sogdiya and Khorezm states. "Temur's rules" is a clear example of this.

A completely new state mechanism is being formed based on the principles of democracy and the separation of powers, the primacy of the law and the Constitution. In a democratic state, human rights and freedoms are reliably protected, and the state provides support for him to lead a decent life. Such a development is a guarantee of ensuring a decent life in Uzbekistan, the rise of national traditions and culture, and the restoration of spiritual and moral values. The Universal Declaration of Human Rights was the first international legal document added after the Republic of Uzbekistan gained independence. Having chosen the path of establishing a democratic, legal state, a strong civil society, Uzbekistan has defined human rights and interests as the most priority direction of the development of society and state building as well as its internal and foreign policy. In the book "New Uzbekistan Strategy" by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Sh. Mirziyoev, "Man, his rights and happiness should be the most important goal of state policy and the activities of all state bodies. It was emphasized that the construction

of society and state policy should be based on this idea and should be organized on the basis of the principle "The state is for the people", which indicates the need to turn human rights and interests into the main criteria of state policy and reforms.

A right is a freedom that extends to a person's natural needs, his value system, and is limited by rules that do not harm the rights of another person. The law implemented by the state is a formal and systematic reflection of the law. All the necessary conditions have been created for the development of the legal culture of the population through the practice of legal relations. The National Center for Human Rights, the Ombudsman Institute, and the appropriate commission of the Parliament were formed. Currently, Uzbekistan has joined more than 80 international documents on human rights, including 7 basic UN treaties and 4 optional protocols. Ensuring basic rights and freedoms is very important in the reforms in Uzbekistan. The reforms have a positive effect on the interests of all sections of the population.

After the independence of Uzbekistan, the judicial system in the country was recognized as one of the areas that should be fundamentally reformed. This issue became more relevant in the process of abandoning the administrative-command management system and establishing a democratic legal state and civil society based on a developed market economy. Reforms have been implemented step by step to strengthen the rule of law, the protection of the rights and interests of individuals, society and the state, increase the legal consciousness and legal culture of the population. As a result of this, conditions were created for further development of social relations, deepening of democratic changes, strengthening of guarantees of protection of universal values, most importantly, the protection of an individual, his life, freedom, honor, dignity and other fundamental rights.

In Uzbekistan, the supremacy of universally recognized principles and norms of international law is recognized on the constitutional basis. Today, our country regularly fulfills its international obligations by ratifying more than 70 international

documents on personal rights, in particular, 10 binding international treaties on human rights adopted by the UN.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, we can say that in our country, which recognizes the value of human rights, it is significant for us to understand that the value of human rights and value is a supreme blessing when personal rights are implemented in accordance with international standards. In our country, all the legal bases for the protection of personal rights and interests have been created and guaranteed, and all the reforms being implemented serve the noble purpose of ensuring and protecting human rights and interests. This shows that it has made significant progress in the field of personal rights

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